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ENHANCING THE LEGAL REVIEW OF AUTONOMOUS WEAPON SYSTEMS

REPORT OF AN EXPERT MEETING
(SYDNEY, 28–30 MARCH 2023)

Netta Goussac
Natalia Jevglevskaja
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Law and the Future of War Research Group

Based at The University of Queensland's TC Beirne School of Law, the Law and the Future of War Research Group investigates the diverse ways in which law constrains, enables or ignores technological change in the context of national and global security. The Group focuses particularly on the legal challenges posed by autonomous functions of military platforms, systems and weapons.

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The views and opinions expressed are those of the authors, and do not necessarily reflect the views of the Australian Government or any other government or organisation whose representatives participated in their personal capacities in the Expert Meeting.

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Abbreviations

AI	artificial intelligence
AP I	Protocol (I) Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and Relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts
AWS	autonomous weapon system(s)
GGE	Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IHL	international humanitarian law
LAWS	lethal autonomous weapon system(s)
TEVV	testing, evaluation, verification, and validation
UK	United Kingdom
US	United States

Executive Summary

This report provides a summary of an expert meeting on the legal review of autonomous weapon systems ('AWS'), which was convened by the Australian Defence Force in Sydney on 28–30 March 2023 ('Expert Meeting'). The meeting was attended by 32 experts, including from six States (Australia, Brazil, New Zealand, Sweden, the United Kingdom and the United States), the International Committee of the Red Cross, non-governmental organisations, academia and the defence industry.

During the meeting, States' experts gave an overview of current national practices relating to the tailoring of legal reviews for the purposes of reviewing AWS. The participants identified and discussed challenges in conducting legal reviews for AWS as compared to weapon systems without autonomous features. They also considered the possibility of creating a standing mechanism for the exchange of best practices in relation to legal reviews.

A discussion of **national practices** suggested that there were broad similarities in the steps that States adopted as part of their legal review processes. At the same time, there are significant differences in the exact scope and methodology of the reviews. That States are still contemplating how to best examine autonomous functionality in the context of legal reviews underlines the utility and timeliness of information exchange in this context.

The meeting identified and discussed challenges associated with the legal review of an AWS. Some of the more significant of these challenges were discussed in detail, and are summarised in this report. These **key challenges** overlap in that they are tied to articulating how the presence of autonomy in a weapon system poses difficulties for existing methodologies for legal reviews. The discussions suggested that these key challenges required consideration of alternative approaches in the development or adaptation of States' legal review processes as they relate to AWS.

The key challenges are:

- delimiting the nature and scope of the legal review, considering that the basis for conducting legal reviews differs from State to State, and that autonomy relates to particular functions of a system or system of systems;
- identifying the contextual information needed to conduct a legal review of an AWS, considering that assessing the consistency of autonomous functionality with international humanitarian law may require a broader analysis than is normally undertaken in a legal review;
- establishing the boundaries and interactions between legal reviews and the provision of operational legal advice, given the functioning of the AWS or the environment in which it operates may change during its deployment;
- identifying what might constitute a modification of an AWS that necessitates further review;

- addressing the types of AWS-specific technological issues that might affect the manner in which legal compliance can be assessed during a legal review; and
- addressing persistent challenges in reviewing AWS by examining whether challenges that have been raised in the debate relating to AWS-specific legal reviews are the same as for other weapons, means and methods of warfare.

Many meeting participants noted that improved transparency and information-sharing in relation to legal reviews of AWS could contribute to improving States' practices; promote universalisation of legal reviews among States that do not currently conduct them; and act as a trust and confidence-building measure. Participants broke down what information could be shared by States and how that information could be shared, drawing a distinction between, on the one hand, information about how a legal review of an AWS is conducted and, on the other hand, information about a specific legal review of an AWS.

The report includes at Annex A a set of **Elements of Possible Good Practices** ('Elements') that may assist States in carrying out legal reviews of AWS in a manner that accounts for the unique challenges posed by these weapon systems. They may also enhance the efficacy of legal reviews as a mechanism for implementing international legal obligations relevant to AWS. The Elements relate to the nature and scope of the review; the conduct of the review (including relevant general considerations and questions relating to the modification of capabilities); the process of the review (including timing, participants, methods and connection to other processes); and transparency and information exchange. As originally drafted, the Elements reflected an analysis of submissions made in the Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems in relation to the practicalities of legal reviews. The authors of this report then refined the Elements in light of the discussions at the Expert Meeting and further input from participants and expert peer reviewers.

The authors hope that this report will provide States with a useful basis for continuing to address the challenges of legal reviews of AWS, build good practices and work towards regular information exchange. The Elements can also provide immediate food for thought for States that are looking to update, supplement or more effectively implement their existing legal review processes to better account for autonomy in weapon systems.

The authors of this report recommend that a follow-up meeting with broader participation be convened in 2024 in order to:

- **continue constructive discussions in relation to conducting legal reviews of AWS and facilitating voluntary information exchange on legal review processes; and**
- **consider the Elements of Possible Good Practices with a view to developing them into a document that States can use to inform national legal review processes.**

Preface

The legal review of weapons is an important national process. Regardless of whether legal reviews are conducted as a legal obligation or national policy, they are necessary to determine whether the use of a weapon in armed conflict would, in some or all circumstances, be prohibited by international law.

Enduring questions about how international humanitarian law is to be interpreted and applied with respect to autonomous weapon systems (AWS) emphasises the importance of the national legal review processes. In light of this, many States have called for a voluntary exchange of best practices. Such an exchange could assist in the development of robust national legal review processes, build confidence in legal reviews and help ensure the lawful development and use of AWS.

To provide a forum to discuss a voluntary exchange of best practices, the Directorate of Operations and International Law, within the Australian Department of Defence's Defence Legal, proposed an initial expert meeting on the legal review of AWS. Experts from States, non-government organisations, academia and industry were invited to discuss how a mechanism for the voluntary exchange could be established, to identify common understandings and challenges, and discuss the elements of best practices.

The expert meeting provided a great deal of constructive discussion. I am grateful to the authors, Netta Goussac, Natalia Jevglevskaja, Rain Liivoja and Lauren Sanders, who have captured the important outcomes of the expert meeting, and to the participants who provided useful feedback on the draft. I hope that this Report stimulates ongoing discussion on this important topic, and creates a platform to aid the development of best practice among States with respect to legal reviews of AWS.

Damian Copeland

Colonel

Director of Operations and International Law

Australian Defence Force

1 Introduction

1.1 BACKGROUND

Under international humanitarian law ('IHL'), the right of parties to an armed conflict to choose their means and methods of warfare is not unlimited.¹ States have placed constraints on this choice by agreeing to prohibit or limit the use of particular categories of weapons, and by developing general rules that prohibit the use of weapons, means and methods of warfare that have certain effects.

A key mechanism for implementing these rules at the national level is the review of new weapons, means or methods of warfare to determine whether they can be used in compliance with States' obligations under international law – 'legal review' for short. These legal reviews can be part of a State's general efforts to ensure the effective implementation of its IHL obligations. States Party to Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions ('AP I') have a specific obligation to undertake legal reviews under article 36 of that Protocol.²

The Agenda for Humanitarian Action adopted by the 28th International Conference of the Red Cross and Red Crescent in 2003 established the following goal:

In light of the rapid development of weapons technology and in order to protect civilians from the indiscriminate effects of weapons and combatants from unnecessary suffering and prohibited weapons, all new weapons, means and methods of warfare should be subject to rigorous and multidisciplinary review.³

The agenda proposed concrete actions for achieving this goal,⁴ two of which are especially relevant in the present context:

- 1 See, eg, *Hague Convention (IV) regarding the Laws and Customs of War on Land*, signed 18 October 1907, 205 CTS 277 (entered into force 26 January 1910), Annex: Regulations concerning the Laws and Customs of War on Land, art 22; *Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions of Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May be Deemed to be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects*, opened for signature 10 April 1981, 1342 UNTS 137 (entered into force 10 October 1980), preamble; *Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and Relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I)*, opened for signature 8 June 1977, 1125 UNTS 3 (entered into force 7 December 1978) art 35(1) ('AP I').
- 2 AP I (n 1) art 36: 'In the study, development, acquisition or adoption of a new weapon, means or method of warfare, a High Contracting Party is under an obligation to determine whether its employment would, in some or all circumstances, be prohibited by this Protocol or by any other rule of international law applicable to the High Contracting Party.'
- 3 28th International Conference of the Red Cross and Red Crescent (Geneva, Switzerland, 2–6 December 2003), Resolution 1, Agenda for Humanitarian Action, General objective 2, Final goal 2.5 (Ensure the legality of new weapons under international law) <<https://www.icrc.org/en/doc/resources/documents/resolution/28-international-conference-resolution-1-2003.htm>>.
- 4 Ibid 2.51–2.5.3, pertaining to the conduct of and voluntary exchange of best practices relating to review of new weapons, means and methods of warfare.

- Legal reviews ‘should involve a multidisciplinary approach, including military, legal, environmental and health-related considerations’.⁵
- The International Committee of the Red Cross (‘ICRC’) will ‘facilitate the voluntary exchange of experience on review procedures. States that have review procedures in place are invited to cooperate with the ICRC in this regard.’⁶

Subsequently, the ICRC published ‘A Guide to the Legal Review of New Weapons, Means and Methods of Warfare’⁷ and reportedly continues to facilitate the exchange of legal review practices.⁸ Additional work has been undertaken by other organisations, such as the Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, to operationalise measures to apply legal review to novel technologies.⁹

The Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems (‘GGE’) has, in a number of consensus statements, highlighted the significance of legal reviews in relation to autonomous weapon systems (‘AWS’). In particular, Guiding Principle (e) affirmed by the GGE stipulates:

In accordance with States’ obligations under international law, in the study, development, acquisition, or adoption of a new weapon, means or method of warfare, determination must be made whether its employment would, in some or all circumstances, be prohibited by international law.¹⁰

The GGE has reached consensus on a number of further issues pertaining to the conduct of legal reviews of AWS, namely:

Weapons systems under development, or modification which significantly changes the use of existing weapons systems, must be reviewed as applicable to ensure compliance with IHL.¹¹

Legal reviews, at the national level, in the study, development, acquisition or adoption of a new weapon, means or method of warfare are a useful tool to assess nationally whether potential weapons systems based on emerging technologies in the area of lethal autonomous weapon systems would be prohibited by any rule of international law applicable to that State in all or some circumstances. States are free to independently determine the means to conduct legal reviews although the voluntary exchange of best practices could be beneficial, bearing in mind national security considerations or commercial restrictions on proprietary information.¹²

While GGE participants have noted certain challenges that AWS pose for legal reviews and made submissions on practices States could adopt in order to address these challenges, GGE meetings have not considered these challenges or practices in detail.

1.2 PURPOSE OF THE EXPERT MEETING

The Australian Department of Defence convened the Expert Meeting on the Legal Review of AWS at the Indo-Pacific Centre for Military Law, Victoria Barracks, Sydney,

⁵ Ibid 2.5.1.

⁶ Ibid 2.5.3.

⁷ International Committee of the Red Cross (‘ICRC’), ‘A Guide to the Legal Review of New Weapons, Means and Methods of Warfare: Measures to Implement Article 36 of Additional Protocol I of 1977’ (2006) 88(864) *International Review of the Red Cross* 931 <https://www.icrc.org/en/doc/assets/files/other/irrc_864_icrc_geneva.pdf>.

⁸ The ICRC includes public information about national implementation of IHL in its *National Practice Database* <<https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/national-practice>>.

⁹ See, eg, Vincent Boulanin, *Implementing Article 36 Weapon Reviews in the Light of Increasing Autonomy in Weapon Systems* (Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (‘SIPRI’) Insights on Peace and Security No 2015/1, November 2015) <<https://www.sipri.org/publications/2015/sipri-insights-peace-and-security/implementing-article-36-weapon-reviews-light-increasing-autonomy-weapon-systems>>.

¹⁰ *Meeting of the High Contracting Parties to the Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects (Geneva, 13–15 November 2019): Final Report*, UN Doc CCW/MSP/2019/9 (13 December 2019) annex III, para (e) <<https://undocs.org/CCW/MSP/2019/9>>.

¹¹ *Report of the 2018 session of the Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems*, UN Doc CCW/GGE.1/2018/3 (23 October 2018) para 23(c) <<https://undocs.org/CCW/GGE.1/2018/3>>.

¹² *Report of the 2019 session of the Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems*, UN Doc CCW/GGE.1/2019/3 (25 September 2019) para 17(i) <<https://undocs.org/CCW/GGE.1/2019/3>>.

on 28–30 March 2023 ('Expert Meeting'). The meeting was chaired by Colonel Damian Copeland, Director of Operations and International Law. The 32 attendees of the meeting included experts from six States (including military and civilian personnel responsible for legal reviews), the ICRC, non-governmental organisations, academia and the defence industry. While the majority of the participants were Australian, the meeting did not focus exclusively on Australian practice.

The Expert Meeting sought to build on commonalities that have emerged from State submissions to the GGE relating to the legal review of AWS. State experts shared, on an informal basis, current practices and lessons learned in the creation of policy to implement legal review obligations, especially with a view to conducting legal reviews of capabilities with autonomous functionality. The participants engaged in a discussion about the challenges created for legal review processes by autonomy, possible good practices in relation to the legal review of AWS, and possible mechanisms for improving transparency and exchanging information.

The discussions were based on the premise that legal reviews provide a useful framework for determining whether an AWS is intrinsically illegal, or whether its normal or expected use would in some circumstances be unlawful. Equally, the meeting proceeded on the basis that the development of good practices on legal reviews would complement other efforts aimed at elaborating options related to the normative and operational framework applicable to AWS.

In the course of the discussions, the original objectives and outcomes of the Expert Meeting, as outlined in the preface to this report, were amended. Rather than immediately seeking to develop a document that would outline best practices and the architecture for a mechanism for the voluntary exchange of information, the discussions revolved around how and for what purpose the exchanges could be conducted, and what some of the elements of good practices might be, in light of the challenges identified during the meeting.

1.3 CONTENT AND OBJECTIVES OF THE REPORT

This report seeks to reflect the key issues identified in the discussions at the Expert Meeting, in order to facilitate follow-up meetings on this topic. The report consists of the following main parts:

- a summary of national practices and processes as they relate to the tailoring of legal reviews for the purposes of reviewing AWS (**Part 2**);
- a high-level analysis of the challenges identified by participants at the meeting in the conduct of legal reviews of AWS as compared to weapon systems without autonomous features (**Part 3**);
- reflections on how Guiding Principle (e) could be furthered through the creation of a standing mechanism for the exchange of best practices (**Part 4**).

During the Expert Meeting, participants did not see a need to agree on a definition of AWS. In the view of the authors of this report, the discussions proceeded on the basis of a broad understanding of AWS, which would include all weapon systems that, once activated, are able to select and engage targets without further intervention by an operator.¹³

Attached to the report as **Annex A** are Elements of Possible Good Practices. These are based on a general distillation of commonalities in submissions made to the GGE on legal reviews,¹⁴ analysis and feedback from meeting participants, and further elaboration by the authors of this report.

¹³ A similarly broad understanding is adopted in, eg, US Department of Defense, *DoD Directive 3000.09: Autonomy in Weapons Systems* (25 January 2023) 21 <<https://www.esd.whs.mil/portals/54/documents/dd/issuances/dodd/300009p.pdf>> (defining an AWS as a 'weapon system that, once activated, can select and engage targets without further intervention by an operator') ('*US DoD Directive 3000.09*'); ICRC, *ICRC Position on Autonomous Weapon Systems* (12 May 2021) <<https://www.icrc.org/en/document/icrc-position-autonomous-weapon-systems>> ('Autonomous weapon systems select and apply force to targets without human intervention.').

¹⁴ See the updated primer for the Expert Meeting: Rosie Cavdarski, Lauren Sanders and Rain Liivoja, *Legal Reviews of Autonomous Weapon Systems: Report on Submissions to the GGE on LAWS* (Law and the Future of War Research Group, TC Beirne School of Law, The University of Queensland, ver 2.0, May 2023) <<https://doi.org/10.14264/1c0275b>>.

Annex B contains the list of meeting participants, and **Annex C** provides a selection of other resources that may assist the reader.

This report contains an independent summary of the discussions of the Expert Meeting. The views expressed in this report are those of the authors, informed by the discussions at the meeting. While a draft of this report was circulated among meeting participants, the final report does not seek to reflect consensus views. Furthermore, the meeting was held on the understanding that participant interventions would not be attributed to individuals unless they expressly requested attribution or were explicitly representing State positions. Accordingly, this report does not attribute particular statements to individual participants.

The authors hope that the report will provide States with a useful basis for continuing to address the challenges of legal reviews of AWS, build good practices and work towards regular information exchange. The Elements of Possible Good Practices contained in Annex A may also provide food for thought for States that are looking to update, supplement or more effectively implement their existing legal review processes to better account for autonomy in weapon systems.

2 Overview of National Practices and Processes

This section provides an overview of legal review practices — and for the United States, certain additional review practices — to the extent they were presented, within the time available, by experts from States that participated at the Expert Meeting. These States are listed in alphabetical order.

2.1 AUSTRALIA

In March 2023, Australia revised its Australian Defence Force ('ADF') Guide to the Legal Review of New Weapons, Means or Methods of Warfare ('ADF Guide') developed to enable legal review of a defence capability that is assessed to be a new weapon, means or method of warfare. To the existing two parts — Part 1, which sets out definitions, the process and responsibilities for conducting legal reviews; and Part 2, which explains the scope of article 36 of AP I as traditionally interpreted and applied by Australia — was added a new Part 3, which includes additional considerations required in the review of AWS.

Specifically, Part 3 of the ADF Guide outlines 'a functional review' step which supplements the analysis under Part 2. Where a weapon function (such as target tracking, classification, selection and engagement) is enabled or performed by software or artificial intelligence ('AI'), legal review seeks to determine whether the function (or functions) can be performed in accordance with Australia's obligations under applicable international law. This functional review step first identifies the targeting rules under IHL that govern the specific AWS functions. It then determines whether a commander or operator can rely on the AWS to perform these functions, in the circumstances of the weapon's normal or expected use, in compliance with those IHL rules. This determination considers different operational and environmental contexts. Lastly, it considers whether the AWS can be employed in accordance with other relevant laws and national policies.

The presentation of the Australian process emphasised the importance of conducting legal reviews at relevant stages in the weapon's development and acquisition cycle to identify and address legal and operational risks associated with weapons, including AWS, in a timely fashion. It also considered challenges posed to legal reviews by AWS. In particular, because of the targeting law that needs to be taken into account in the review of AWS, this presentation pointed to a potential overlap in responsibilities of the authority in charge of the legal review under article 36 of AP I and a legal adviser to the commander under article 82 of that Protocol.

Throughout the years, Australia has actively contributed to the discussions of the GGE. In 2018, it described its legal review process as implemented at the time.¹⁵ In 2019, Australia presented its system of control required for any military use of force (including where AWS could be employed) and explained how its legal review process forms part of that control system.¹⁶

Australia also introduced a one-day Article 36 Weapon Review Certification Course run by the Directorate of Operations and International Law to train ADF legal officers to conduct legal reviews. The course is in two parts, with the first part dedicated to the law and the second to practice. The Directorate of Operations and International Law intends to release a public version of this course.

2.2 BRAZIL

The Brazilian system for assessing legality of weapons is reflected in Annex I of Decree No 10.030 of 30 September 2019.¹⁷ Article 2 of Annex I indicates capabilities requiring a review. These are defined as ‘products controlled by the Army Command’, that is, products:

1. ‘exhibiting destructive power’;
2. ‘that may cause harm and damage to persons or property’;
3. ‘the use of which should be restricted for reasons of public safety’; or
4. ‘of military interest’.

Article 18 of Annex I specifies that ‘compliance with the minimum safety and performance requirements’ of those products will be assessed and certified by the Conformity Assessment Authority, which fulfils the requisite accreditation requirements and has been designated to carry out such assessment and certification tasks by the Army Command. Autonomous systems fall under the review scope.

2.3 NEW ZEALAND

The requirements for the legal review process adopted by New Zealand are set out in Chapter 7, Section 4 of the *Manual of Armed Forces Law – Volume 4: Law of Armed Conflict* (‘NZ LOAC Manual’).¹⁸ In conducting legal reviews, so far New Zealand has focused on reviewing conventional weapon systems. The review process is generally initiated by a request for a legal review coming from industry. The review takes into consideration:

1. specific provisions of customary international law and international treaty law applicable to New Zealand;
2. general principles on the use of weapons as reflected in AP I;
3. the Martens Clause; and
4. applicable domestic law and policies.

In particular, as part of the analysis of whether a weapon under review may contravene principles of humanity or the dictates of public conscience, the reviewing authority considers whether a weapon is reflective of values shared by New Zealanders. Such values may be captured in policy statements. For example, while nuclear weapons are not prohibited under customary international law, New Zealand considers the use of any weapon systems with nuclear capabilities as inherently incompatible with societal values of New Zealanders.¹⁹

15 Australia, *The Australian Article 36 Review Process*, UN Doc CCW/GGE.2/2018/WP.6 (30 August 2018) <<https://undocs.org/CCW/GGE.2/2018/WP.6>>.

16 Australia, *Australia’s System of Control and Applications for Autonomous Weapon Systems*, UN Doc CCW/GGE.1/2019/WP.2/Rev.1 (26 March 2019) <<https://undocs.org/CCW/GGE.1/2019/WP.2/Rev.1>>.

17 Regulamento de Produtos Controlados, Decreto nº 10.030 de 30 de setembro 2019 <<https://www.in.gov.br/web/dou/-/decreto-n-10.030-de-30-de-setembro-de-2019-219207086>>.

18 New Zealand Defence Force, *DM 69: Manual of Armed Forces Law – Volume 4: Law of Armed Conflict* (2nd ed, 8 January 2019) <<https://www.onlinelibrary.iihl.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/NZ-Manual-Law-of-Armed-Conflict.pdf>> (‘NZ LOAC Manual’).

19 New Zealand is also party to the *Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons*, opened for signature 7 July 2017, UN Doc A/CONF.229/2017/8 (entered into force 22 January 2021).

2.4 SWEDEN

Sweden implements article 36 through the Ordinance on International Law Review of Weapons Projects.²⁰ The Ordinance establishes the Delegation for International Law Review of Weapons ('Delegation') comprising members from diverse fields of expertise, including law, operations, technology and medical science.

A new 'weapons project' — that is, any project that concerns the study, development, acquisition or modification of weapons or methods of warfare — being considered by the Swedish Armed Forces, the Swedish Defence Materiel Administration, the Swedish Defence Research Agency or other entity must be reported to the Delegation as early as practicable. Along with the weapons (systems) intended to be used by the military, the Delegation may review capabilities intended to be used by other agencies, for example, the Swedish Police Authority, the Swedish Coast Guard and Swedish Customs.

Having considered the weapons project as described by the reporting entity, the Delegation must decide on the project's compliance with Sweden's obligations under international law. Where the weapons project raises compliance concerns, the Delegation must advise the reporting entity to introduce such modifications to the project as may be necessary to ensure that the weapons project is compliant; to issue restrictions on the operational use of a given weapon or consider alternative uses of that weapon; or to consider alternative weapons projects. However, the Delegation has no enforcement powers. The Delegation has a duty to follow up on 'significant' weapons projects that it has previously reviewed.

2.5 UNITED KINGDOM

In the UK, legal reviews are undertaken by military lawyers serving on the staff of the Development, Concepts and Doctrine Centre. The process is described in detail in a document that is publicly accessible.²¹ The review obligation extends to reviewing weapons with novel and technologically advanced processes, which may therefore include those weapons, means and methods with autonomous functions. Legal analysis is focused on the customary international law and international treaty law binding the UK in a situation of armed conflict. In light of the challenges posed to legal reviews by autonomy, the UK believes that legal reviews could benefit from a mechanism that allows the sharing of best practices.

2.6 UNITED STATES

Legal review practices in the US pre-date the adoption of AP I.²² The US is not a State Party to AP I and does not regard article 36 as reflecting customary international law. It engages in a robust practice of conducting reviews of the legality of weapons as a matter of domestic policy,²³ and regards such reviews as good practice to facilitate the implementation of international law applicable to weapons and their use in armed conflict. Each of the military services is responsible for reviewing weapon systems it develops or acquires. The review process considers the following three questions: first, whether the weapon falls within a class of weapons that is specifically prohibited by customary international law and treaty law applicable to the US; second, whether the weapon's intended use is calculated to cause superfluous injury or unnecessary

20 *Förordning om folkrättslig granskning av vapenprojekt* [Ordinance on International Law Review of Weapons Projects] (15 November 2007), Swedish Code of Statutes, SFS 2007:936 <https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/forordning-2007936-om-folkrattslig-granskning_sfs-2007-936>.

21 Development, Concepts and Doctrine Centre, UK Ministry of Defence, *UK Weapon Reviews* (11 March 2016) <https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/507319/20160308-UK_weapon_reviews.pdf>.

22 Office of General Counsel, US Department of Defense, *Law of War Manual* (June 2015, updated December 2016) s 6.2.3 <<https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/pdfs/AD1023075.pdf>>. Ibid ch 6 contains a description of US policy on the review of legality of weapons and details specific weapons it regards as lawful and unlawful as a matter of customary international law and treaty law.

23 US Department of Defense, *DoD Directive 2311.01: DoD Law of War Program* (2 July 2020) ('US DoD Directive 2311.01') <<https://www.esd.whs.mil/Portals/54/Documents/DD/issuances/dodd/231101p.pdf>>; US Department of Defense, *DoD Directive 5000.01: The Defense Acquisition System* (9 September 2020; Change 1, 28 July 2022) <<https://www.esd.whs.mil/Portals/54/Documents/DD/issuances/dodd/500001p.pdf>>.

suffering; and third, whether the weapon is inherently indiscriminate. Further, if the weapon is not prohibited, the review should also consider whether there are other restrictions (eg, domestic law and policy) on the weapon's use that are specific to that type of weapon. Finally, it may be appropriate to advise whether further measures should be taken that would assist in ensuring compliance with law of war obligations related to the type of weapon being acquired or procured.

US Department of Defence ('DoD') *DoD Directive 2311.01: DoD Law of War Program* establishes DoD policy that '[t]he intended acquisition, procurement, or modification of weapons or weapon systems is reviewed for consistency with the law of war'.²⁴ In January 2023, the DoD also revised *DoD Directive 3000.09: Autonomy in Weapon Systems ('US DoD Directive 3000.09')*.²⁵ This directive does not set out practice in conducting legal reviews; rather, it establishes DoD policy and assigns responsibilities for developing and using autonomous and semi-autonomous functions in weapon systems, including armed platforms that are remotely operated or operated by onboard personnel. Among other things, it provides that such systems will undergo rigorous hardware and software verification and validation ('V&V') and realistic system developmental and operational testing and evaluation ('T&E'); and establishes guidelines designed to minimise the probability and consequences of failures in autonomous and semi-autonomous weapon systems that could lead to unintended engagements. *US DoD Directive 3000.09* also establishes the Autonomous Weapon Systems Working Group to support senior authorities in the DoD in considering the full range of relevant DoD interests during the review of AWS and to advise on potential issues presented by such weapons during a potential senior-level policy review in accordance with the directive that would be supplementary to a legal review.

²⁴ *US DoD Directive 2311.01* (n 23).

²⁵ *US DoD Directive 3000.09* (n 13).

3 Challenges Created by Autonomy

3.1 SCOPE AND NATURE OF THE REVIEW PROCESS

Participants in the Expert Meeting noted that for States Party to AP I, the legal review obligation under article 36 relates to weapons as well as means and methods of warfare. This raised questions as to what parts of a ‘weapon system’ — including hardware (such as sensors and platforms) and software necessary for the operation of the ‘weapon’ — require review and, equally, what equipment might be captured by the term ‘system’. Similarly, the related international law term of ‘means of warfare’ remains to be clarified. Yet these questions are particularly relevant to AWS, because essentially any weapon can be integrated into a system with autonomous functions.

The notion of lethality, which has featured in the title, mandate and discussions of the GGE, did not arise during the meeting. This aligns with the widely accepted view that whether a capability may be expected to cause death does not determine whether it requires a legal review. The anticipated lethality may well play an important role in the legal assessment of the capability (eg, in relation to the prohibition of superfluously injurious weapons), but the capability may amount to a weapon, means or method of warfare without directly causing lethal effects.

Many participants acknowledged that the legal review of AWS creates new challenges. However, the idea that this necessitated an entirely separate review process was not entertained. Rather, the participants considered what these challenges were and how they could be addressed within the existing review mechanisms. In other words, participants approached the problem as one of potentially adjusting existing processes rather than creating new ones.

In the view of some participants, a broader AWS-specific legal analysis, mentioned in subsection 3.2 below, could be undertaken as part of an additional stage in the established legal review procedure. Thus, for example, the revisions to the Australian legal review process, discussed in the meeting, introduce a further step for analysing the autonomous functions of weapon systems (see subsection 2.1 above). A difficulty with this approach is the need to define which weapon systems qualify as AWS for the purposes of that additional step. The same problem would present even more acutely if an entirely separate review process was introduced for AWS. This problem could be mitigated by subjecting every weapon system with any algorithmic processing in its targeting functions to an additional review step or separate review process, irrespective of the degree of autonomy the system would have as a result of such processing.

Finally, some States might not consider it necessary or advisable to address all relevant normative frameworks or standards in the legal review process. For example, the US military has an additional policy requirement for review and approval by certain

senior DoD officials before developing and fielding certain AWS.²⁶ This review considers, *inter alia*, whether a range of policy standards have been met.

3.2 CONTEXTUAL INFORMATION AND ANALYSIS

Many meeting participants emphasised the importance of considering the context of the normal or intended use of the AWS for completing a legal review. The system may have been developed for a particular use case (that is, use in a particular domain of warfare, or against particular types of targets) and would perform differently in a different context.

For some participants, evaluating this context and assessing the system's use in that context was already an aspect of the established legal review methodology. In their view, a reviewer needs to ascertain whether the commander or operator is capable of using the system while fulfilling all the requirements of the rules that govern the conduct of hostilities. With respect to weapons that have no autonomous functionality, the need to consider these rules in detail at the legal review stage has generally been limited.²⁷ This may be different when it comes to AWS. The ability of an AWS to perform functions that would otherwise require direct human involvement may necessitate the consideration of context-dependent rules on the conduct of hostilities in relation to the intended use case.

One participant emphasised in this context that the rule prohibiting the use of inherently indiscriminate weapons is, under AP I, an aspect of the prohibition of indiscriminate attacks.²⁸ This suggests that there is no sharp divide between rules concerning the legality of weapons (sometimes referred to as 'weapons law') and the rules relating to the conduct of hostilities (sometimes called 'targeting law').

Other participants took the view that existing legal review processes would need to be adjusted so as to more fully consider targeting law in addition to weapons law, where the autonomous functionality of the weapon system may affect its use under those rules. Others still argued that it was inappropriate to expand legal review to targeting law matters, as this was more appropriately the purview of operational legal advice.

3.3 LEGAL REVIEWS AND OPERATIONAL LEGAL ADVICE

Some participants distinguished between the conduct of a legal review and the need to provide operational legal advice about the lawful operation of a weapon, means or method of warfare in a particular context.

This distinction interacted with the need to understand the minimum contextual information required for undertaking an effective review to assess whether the AWS can be used in compliance with IHL when deployed (see subsection 3.2 above). Some participants noted that the review of an AWS must be conducted in general terms, while the obligation to ensure its lawful use remains the commander's during deployment. Other participants pointed to the existing arrangements for commanders to undertake that assessment with the assistance of deployed legal advice (whether pursuant to article 82 of AP I or as part of national efforts to implement the State's IHL obligations).

Some participants suggested that this obligation to ensure that the AWS is used lawfully could necessitate the sharing of the context and outcomes of legal reviews, including considerations relevant to the analysis, more broadly among legal advisers than currently is the case. Some participants noted that militaries that undertake legal reviews operate on the basis that if a weapon is deployed in accordance with its normal and expected use, there is a presumption of legal regularity in terms of its op-

²⁶ *US DoD Directive 3000.09* (n 13) s 4.

²⁷ But see ICRC (n 7) 943: '[T]hese rules are also relevant to the assessment of the legality of a new weapon before it has been used on the battlefield, to the extent that the characteristics, expected use and foreseeable effects of the weapon allow the reviewing authority to determine whether or not the weapon will be capable of being used lawfully in certain foreseeable situations and under certain conditions.'

²⁸ See AP I (n 1) art 51(4)(b) and (c).

eration, in which it is expected that personnel using the weapon system will exercise discretion in complying with IHL, including the rules of distinction, proportionality and precautions in attack. In contrast, with weapons that are intended to be used with reliance on autonomous functionality to select and engage targets, the discretion that would normally be exercised by operators to ensure compliance with legal requirements might not be exercised in the usual way.

A number of participants identified the need to ensure users of an AWS and their supporting legal advisers understood the conditions for which the AWS had been reviewed, such as the particular operational conditions, command and control arrangements, or threat context, and the limitations or restrictions on the use provided by the reviewer when approving the weapon. Participants noted that this type of information would facilitate an understanding of when to conduct a further review of the AWS or if there was simply a requirement to provide operational legal advice about the use of the AWS.

3.4 MODIFICATIONS SUBJECT TO FURTHER REVIEW

Participants generally agreed that in the case of modifications to an AWS a further legal review may be required. Examples considered by participants included modifications to system sensors, data, models, algorithms, algorithmic decision thresholds, intended mission sets, intended operational environments (including physical and cyber environments), intended target sets and expected adversarial countermeasures. In that regard, a number of participants lauded the US approach to reviewing modifications to weapon systems.²⁹

Some participants raised concerns as to how often modifications to an AWS could or should be reviewed, in particular as States may be constrained in resources (including personnel and time) to carry out further legal reviews. It was acknowledged, however, that legal reviews constitute ‘risk management’ or ‘risk mitigation’ tools, meaning that it would be in the direct interest of States to review AWS as often as necessary to avert any adverse consequences that they may trigger.

Some participants noted that review of certain minor or incremental modifications could be delegated to a legal adviser situated closer to the operational setting in which an AWS is deployed. Yet some others pointed out the challenges for operational legal advisers to conduct an effective review of the AWS, such as those that stem from persistent challenges like potentially limited or no access to empirical information or the relevant subject-matter expertise (see subsection 3.6), or inability to access existing legal review(s) of the AWS to ensure coherence in its assessment.

One participant noted the ability to divorce the development and assessment of software upgrades from the development and assessment of upgrades to the system as a whole. In that regard, some participants questioned whether ‘real time’ software upgrades aimed at enabling, for example, the AWS to adapt to changing operational environments should be reviewed ‘constantly’, that is, in ‘real time’, especially if the potential for adaptation had been considered as part of the initial review, and whether such constant reviews would be feasible or appropriate. Yet again, some other participants observed that certain software could be employed in such circumstances to assess whether an AWS continues to perform some or all of its functions within specified legal and operational parameters, and to communicate the results of the assessment to the human operating the AWS.

Many participants acknowledged that where modifications are ‘significant’, ‘substantial’ or ‘material’, a further legal review must take place. While there was no agreement as to what specifically falls under the scope of such ‘significant’, ‘substantial’, or ‘material’ modifications, examples discussed by participants included changes to the intended use of an AWS (eg, where an AWS that operates on machine learning software is put into an environment for which it was not initially trained) and changes to the effects that an AWS was designed to produce. Some participants also noted that if the system’s potential for modifications was considered as part of the initial review and the actual modifications fell within the parameters approved in that initial review,

29 US DoD Directive 2311.01 (n 23).

review of such modifications would be unnecessary to ensure compliance with the State's obligations under applicable international law.

3.5 TECHNOLOGICAL ISSUES

Participants discussed the limits of existing review processes as they related to AWS legal review. They identified a number of technical and technological issues associated with the use or incorporation of autonomy that may have unique impacts upon the legal review process. Some of the challenges mentioned by participants can be captured by the following questions:

- What part(s) of the AWS fulfils critical functions (that constitute the weapon, means or method of warfare) relevant to compliance with IHL and therefore need to be considered the subject of the legal review?
- When are changes to human-machine interaction consistent with legal obligations? For example, how might moving from an operator on the loop, to an operator in the loop, change what is needed to meet legal requirements?
- What constitutes a change to the system that necessitates a further legal review? For example, does a software update that results in changes to the system's AI processes, so that it falls outside the parameters that were considered and approved in the initial legal review, necessitate a new review?
- How can the legal review consider technical aspects of the system and its performance (specifically related to autonomous functionality), such as how the system deals with technical challenges associated with AI processes (eg unintended AI bias, out-of-date or corrupt data)?
- How can independent testing, evaluation, verification and validation processes be incorporated into the legal review?
- How should the legal review account for technological and practical limitations in the methodology of testing? Examples include the limitations on live testing and edge-case testing of AWS, and the suitability of simulation/virtual testing in providing evidence of an appropriately high quality to enable review.
- What testing and scoping of the software in the system needs to be conducted for the purposes of the legal review? How might this differ where the software involves AI or machine learning capabilities?
- How should the legal review requirements related to testing the interaction of the AWS with external information feeds (eg, data sets or sensors) be articulated?

One participant suggested, with the support of some others, that the ability to articulate required behaviours of an AWS at the initial design specification stage (referred to in the Australian context as the Functional Performance Standards), would enable industry to 'build in' the requirements for the system, to subsequently enable the user to comply with legal obligations; and would also provide a methodology to enable a certification process associated with that legal compliance. Several industry participants noted that there are pre-existing verification processes, tools and methods that can provide evidence to support verification of the capacity to comply with legal standards; rather than there being no methodology to assess capacity for legal compliance, the issue relates to a need to articulate legal requirements early during the design process.

Other participants pointed to the use of a common language — by adopting existing standards (eg, IEEE standards)³⁰ or articulating standards specific to AWS³¹ — as a further method to enable verification of compliance.

30 See, eg, *IEEE Standard 7000-2021: IEEE Standard Model Process for Addressing Ethical Concerns during System Design* (16 June 2021) <<https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEESTD.2021.9536679>>; *IEEE Standard 7001-2021: IEEE Standard for Transparency of Autonomous Systems* (4 March 2022) <<https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEESTD.2022.9726144>>; *IEEE Standard 7007-2021: IEEE Ontological Standard for Ethically Driven Robotics and Automation Systems* (12 November 2021) <<https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEESTD.2021.9611206>>.

31 See, eg, *US DoD Directive 3000.09* (n 13) 7 (articulated metrics) and 14 (V&V and T&E requirements).

3.6 PERSISTENT CHALLENGES

While some of the challenges of reviewing the legality of AWS are related to the unique characteristics of those systems, other challenges raised by meeting participants are related to all legal reviews. These ‘persistent challenges’ are a reminder that conducting effective legal reviews of any weapon, means or method of warfare can be demanding — the presence of autonomy merely adds a layer of complexity.

Participants raised three examples that illustrate these persistent challenges. First is the challenge of accessing **empirical evidence** during the legal review process, particularly at the early stages of development or acquisition. To conduct a review effectively, a reviewer should examine documentation from the manufacturer on the characteristics and performance of the AWS, as well as the results of tests and evaluations. Some participants indicated that a legal reviewer who is faced with a lack of empirical evidence may find it necessary to caveat their conclusions, potentially limiting the utility of that legal review.

A second persistent challenge relates to the ability to obtain input from **subject-matter experts other than legal experts** in the legal review process, such as experts on algorithms, military tactics, and environmental or health considerations. The importance of a multidisciplinary approach to legal reviews had been emphasised by States as early as the 28th International Conference of the Red Cross and Red Crescent in 2003 (see subsection 1.1 above). Some participants noted that such multidisciplinaryity was difficult to achieve in practice. The reasons were variously attributed to a lack of relevant expertise within the government system or to the limited time or resources dedicated to conducting legal reviews.

The third persistent challenge is that of identifying whether and how to consider in the legal review **rules or standards from sources other than international law**.³² Participants expressed divergent views on whether a legal review should consider national laws, anticipated developments in international law, ethical considerations and — as referenced in some interpretations of the Martens Clause — the principles of humanity and the dictates of public conscience.³³ For example, in Australia and New Zealand, potential future developments of the law are considered as part of the legal review.³⁴ The *NZ LOAC Manual* helpfully explains the utility of this by noting that ‘[a]n international trend towards the prohibition of a particular weapon or munition may be discernible before a comprehensive ban comes into effect’.³⁵ Australia, New Zealand and the US often address domestic policy guidance in their legal reviews.

Participants who indicated that some or all of these sources were relevant to the legal review nonetheless acknowledged the challenge of identifying and applying these rules or standards in the legal review process. Several participants urged caution in the incorporation of non-legal considerations into the legal review process, which might lead it to be seen as a panacea. One participant accepted that legal reviewers may have regard to non-legal sources but could not form conclusions based on such considerations. Others agreed with the proposition that where the legal review does consider non-legal factors, the reviewer should make it clear which conclusions are reached on the basis of binding law, and which on the basis of policy, ethical, or other considerations.

³² This is distinct from the use of secondary sources in the course of treaty interpretation.

³³ AP I (n 1) art 1.

³⁴ *NZ LOAC Manual* (n 18) para 7.4.2.

³⁵ *Ibid* n 21.

4 Information Sharing and Transparency

Discussions at the Expert Meeting about the potential for greater transparency in relation to legal reviews of AWS examined what information could be shared, and the potential incentives for greater transparency.

Some participants posited that States may be reluctant to share information about legal reviews due to national security and proprietary sensitivities (though others suggested these oft-cited reasons could benefit from closer examination, and that it may be possible for both States and industry actors to be more transparent). One participant suggested a more practical reason as possibly contributing to a lack of openness: a lack of continuity among officials tasked with conducting legal reviews. Another participant suggested that legal reviews could be a topic of discussion at the national rather than the international level, given the different legal and policy positions among States.

Nonetheless, many participants indicated that a general exchange of information would be useful, particularly in relation to legal reviews of AWS. Three key incentives were posited for improved transparency:

1. to improve State practices, overcome challenges and develop tools relating to legal reviews, including legal reviews of AWS;
2. to promote legal reviews among States who do not conduct them, and to support their training needs; and
3. to be a trust and confidence-building measure.

Further discussions at the meeting aimed to break down what information could be shared by States, and how that information could be shared. Participants drew a distinction between, on the one hand, information about *how* States conduct legal reviews of AWS and, on the other hand, information about a *specific* legal review of an AWS.

In relation to the former category of information (*how* legal reviews are conducted), States Party to AP I are required to exchange information on the laws and regulations they adopt to give effect to the Protocol.³⁶ Some participants called for a more systematic exchange among States that conduct legal reviews of AWS (notwithstanding their adherence to AP I) involving States establishing and contributing to, for example, a repository of information about their processes and good practices, or a forum for continued discussions about legal reviews of AWS. Participants suggested that existing information-sharing models could be applied to the subject of legal reviews, including those used by the Missile Technology Control Regime, the Arms Trade Treaty's Diversion Information Exchange Platform, the Multilateral Industrial Security Working Group, the Proliferation Security Initiative and the Montreux Document Fo-

³⁶ See AP I (n 1) art 84.

rum. One participant suggested that the goal of improved information-sharing could be the subject of States' pledges at the International Conference of the Red Cross and Red Crescent in 2024.

In relation to the latter category of information (*specific* legal reviews), some participants noted that, even with due regard to national security and proprietary sensitivities, States could share select information about specific legal reviews. Others felt reviews would often remain privileged or otherwise subject to protection pursuant to national requirements.

5 Recommendations

This report summarises the discussions of the Expert Meeting relating to the legal review of AWS held at the initiative of the Australian Defence Force in March 2023.

Noting the objectives and outcomes of this meeting, the authors of this report recommend that another meeting be convened in 2024 in order to:

- continue constructive discussions in relation to conducting legal reviews of AWS and facilitating voluntary information exchange on legal review processes; and
- consider the Elements of Possible Good Practices annexed to this report with a view to developing them into a document that States can use to inform national legal review processes.

The next meeting should have broader State and non-State participation and its outcomes documented in a further report in the interests of transparency.

Annexes

A Elements of Possible Good Practices

Purpose

This annex contains a list of good practices that the authors suggest may assist States in carrying out legal reviews of autonomous weapon systems ('AWS') in a manner that accounts for the unique challenges posed by these weapon systems. This list has been drafted on the basis of submissions made in the Group of Governmental Experts on Lethal Autonomous Weapon Systems ('GGE') and refined based on the discussions during the Expert Meeting in Sydney in March 2023.

The list of good practices aims to capture trends or convergences in the views of States. However, it does not necessarily reflect established State practice or any clear agreement between States. This approach seeks to support States in operationalising Guiding Principle (e) of the Guiding Principles developed by the GGE. This is without prejudice to efforts aimed at clarifying or further developing the current normative framework and agreeing on regulations and controls of AWS.

Also, the good practices do not purport to offer an interpretation of existing legal obligations. Indeed, the obligations of States differ when it comes to legal reviews: in particular, not all States are party to Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions ('AP I'), article 36 of which creates a binding obligation to conduct a legal review of weapon systems, including AWS. The practices suggested in this document could be relevant to all States reviewing AWS, irrespective of whether they have an obligation under international law to do so, and what the scope of that obligation might be. Some States may view some of the practices as flowing from their international legal obligations.

Adoption of these practices can, in the view of the drafters, enhance the efficacy of legal reviews as a mechanism for implementing international legal obligations relevant to AWS. This list of practices is not comprehensive, and is intended for consideration and refinement by States. Considering that legal reviews are undertaken at the national level and that States have significant discretion in terms of the conduct of the reviews, they could adopt some or all of these practices voluntarily, or seek agreement with other States.

Terminology

There is no internationally agreed definition of the term 'autonomous weapon system'. In these good practices, the term refers broadly to any weapon system that, once activated, can select and engage targets without further intervention by an operator. Thus, for the purposes of these good practices, AWS include systems with varying degrees of autonomy. These practices are not intended to be limited to 'lethal autonomous weapon systems' ('LAWS'), a concept used by the GGE.

All AWS, whether capable of lethal effects or not, can create challenges for legal review. In addition, the lack of a lethal effect does not absolve States of their obligations to use weapons consistently with international law, or of any obligation to pre-emptively review the weapon. Possibly because of these reasons, the question of lethality did not arise during the Expert Meeting, and that factor is therefore not separately addressed in the proposed good practices.

The reference to ‘weapon systems’ indicates that the focus is broader than just the weapon itself (such as a munition). The ‘system’ includes other hardware (eg, sensors and platforms) and software necessary for the operation of the weapon. Importantly, autonomous targeting capability may be enabled at the system-of-systems level rather than through the interaction of subsystems of a single weapon system or platform. There was no agreement at the Expert Meeting as to what equipment might be captured by the term ‘system’ or the related international law term ‘means of warfare’.

These good practices refer to the pre-emptive assessment of weapons, means and methods of warfare for compliance with international law as ‘legal review’. This term was preferred over the notion of ‘article 36 review’ because it covers review processes undertaken without any obligation under AP I. Also, ‘legal review’ was seen as preferable to ‘weapons review’ as the purpose of the review is to assess legal compliance; where non-legal considerations are included in the review, they play a secondary role.

Scope of the legal review

1. A State could conduct a legal review, including the review of an AWS, as a result of the State’s:
 - a. specific obligation under international law to undertake the review;
 - b. interpretation of its general obligations to implement international humanitarian law (‘IHL’); and/or
 - c. national law or policy.
2. The legal review should identify and assess issues of international law compliance specific to AWS.
3. The legal review should assess whether the AWS can be used in compliance with the reviewing State’s applicable international legal obligations. In addition to IHL, these legal obligations may arise from, for example, arms control and disarmament law, international human rights law, international environmental law, law of the sea, space law and *jus contra bellum*.
4. The legal review of an AWS could assess the ability of the AWS to be used in compliance with rules relating to the conduct of hostilities. This may require considering each anticipated method of use of the AWS.
5. States could articulate criteria for determining which capabilities and systems, including those with autonomous functions, amount to weapons, means or methods of warfare and therefore should be the subject of a legal review.

Conducting a legal review

Relevant considerations

6. A legal review of an AWS could assess the human-machine interaction to determine whether humans will be able to fulfil their obligations under international law in the use of AWS.
7. A legal review of an AWS could assess if, where and how its use would transfer responsibility for acts necessary for complying with international law from one human to another human, and whether such a transfer would be consistent with international law.
8. A legal review of an AWS could include a reflection upon additional considerations that the State deems relevant to its use, such as:
 - a. policy constraints;
 - b. domestic law;

- c. security and proliferation risk;
 - d. ethical and societal implications;
 - e. possible future development of the law.
9. Where a legal review addresses issues not based on an international law obligation, the review could make that explicit.
 10. A legal review could conclude that the capability's normal or anticipated use is:
 - a. lawful; or
 - b. lawful under certain circumstances or subject to certain conditions; or
 - c. unlawful.
 11. With respect to the study, development, acquisition and use of AWS, the conditions imposed as a result of the legal review could relate to, for example:
 - a. the characteristics of a system under development;
 - b. the operating environment (such as the type of armed conflict);
 - c. the approved use case(s) (such as use in a particular domain of warfare, or against particular types of targets);
 - d. the approved methods of use;
 - e. degree and type of human-machine interaction;
 - f. the system(s) within which the capability may be integrated.

Modifications

12. States could articulate what kind of changes would cause the legal review to become inadequate, so as to require a reconsideration of the existing legal review, including:
 - a. changes to the applicable law;
 - b. modifications to a capability or its normal or expected use, following its introduction to service.
13. With respect to AWS, such modifications could include changes to:
 - a. the nature and extent of human-machine interaction;
 - b. system algorithms and datasets;
 - c. intended mission sets;
 - d. intended operational environments;
 - e. intended target sets;
 - f. expected adversarial countermeasures.
14. States could also identify appropriate safeguards or risk-mitigation measures with respect to the use of technological processes (such as artificial intelligence techniques) that result in modifications.

Legal review process

Timing

15. States could commence legal reviews of AWS as early as feasible in the study, development and acquisition processes. States could reconsider legal reviews as often as necessary.

Relationship to other national practices

16. States could articulate how legal reviews are integrated into their broader weapons design and development processes.
17. States could communicate the outcomes of legal reviews to those involved in the review process, as well as operational legal advisers and commanders. This could be facilitated by establishing an appropriately controlled national repository to ensure previous legal reviews can easily be found and accessed.
18. States could articulate how legal reviews interact with other policy, administrative and technical frameworks, including control and risk-mitigation measures, in the broader weapons acquisition and use processes.

Participants

19. States could determine the required qualifications of legal reviewers.
20. States could articulate how and by whom legal reviews, including reviews of an AWS or modifications of an AWS, are authorised.
21. States could specify the national authorities for approving modifications and the legal advice required.
22. States could articulate ways to ensure that the legal review takes a multidisciplinary approach capable of properly assessing functions of the AWS that may affect the user's ability to comply with IHL.

Testing, evaluation, verification and validation

23. States could articulate the requirements for reliable and independent testing, evaluation, verification and validation ('TEVV') of AWS to inform the legal review. States could identify and require the use of:
 - a. specific TEVV procedures, methods, environments and protocols;
 - b. specific standards or models of performance, including in relation to reliability and predictability.
24. States could independently evaluate:
 - a. algorithms and training data sets;
 - b. context or use-cases for an AWS.
25. States could articulate what information they require to undertake such evaluations.
26. States could specify the extent to which TEVV of an AWS may be automated.

Sharing information about legal reviews

27. An exchange of information pertaining to legal review processes could occur as a result of States':
 - a. obligations under international law to communicate to each other information about laws and regulations giving effect to IHL;
 - b. decision to engage, on a voluntary basis, in a broader exchange of information and good practices.
28. An exchange of information pertaining to legal review processes could improve their effectiveness. In relation to AWS, such an exchange could include information about:
 - a. if and how the legal review of an AWS differs from a legal review process of a capability that is not an AWS;
 - b. what challenges have arisen in conducting legal reviews of AWS;
 - c. what novel legal issues have required consideration during the legal review of an AWS.
29. States could establish, and contribute to, a repository for information about processes and practices of legal reviews.
30. Having due regard to national security requirements and the protection of proprietary information, States could also add to the repository select information relating to specific legal reviews of particular AWS. This could include outlining the general type of AWS capabilities, functionality or use contexts that a State considers to be consistent or inconsistent with its obligations under international law.

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